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Promoting the human factor in building the Vietnam people's army in the new era

Abstract. The human factor as well as promoting it in all aspects of social life have long played a crucial role in the development of each nation around the world. Having full awareness of its importance, in the course of leading the revolution in Vietnam, The Communist Party of Vietnam has given many guidelines as well as policies suitable to the promotion of the human factor in building and developing the country. The cause of constructing and protecting the country in the new era calls for more extensive diffusion and more creative exercise of the Party's guidelines in creating a «revolutionary, regular, elite and gradually modernized» Vietnam People's Army. In this paper, the author provides a brief summary of the development in the Communist Party of Vietnam's awareness on promoting the human factor from the beginning of our nation's reform until now, with which the author relates to its importance as well as proposing some possible solutions to enhance the role of the human factor in the operation of the Vietnam People's Army and meet the requirements of the new era.

Key words: human, the human factor, embrace the human factor, the army, building the army, the human factor in the army, building the army in the new age.

On the basis of the exercise and creative development of the Marxist-Leninist ideology on the matter of human and the human factor, during the different stages of Vietnam's revolution, the Communist Party of Vietnam has successfully utilized the strength of each Vietnamese individual and the nation as a whole for the cause of liberation. Since the beginning of its leadership in the national reform, the Party has always acknowledged the people's liberation and comprehensive development as the most important objective of the Vietnam revolution. The human factor is not just the aim of the development, but also an

essential driving force in fulfilling the motto: «Wealthy people, strong country, just and civilized society». Therefore, «the Party has stated: The most precious, decisive resource is the Vietnamese people; the human factor is the source of the nation's internal force» [7, p. 6], which, together with other factors, form the motivation for the revolution in Vietnam.

The view of Communist Party of Vietnam on the promotion of the human factor in the cause of national reform.

In the process of the reforms, for the first time, the subject of promoting the human factor was specifically and directly

acknowledged in the *Platform for building the nation in the transition period to socialism* (approved in the Seventh National Congress of the Communist Party of Vietnam), which is quoted as follows: «Promoting the human factor on the basis of guaranteeing citizens' equity and equality of rights and duties; combining economic growth with social progress; material life with spiritual life; meeting the immediate needs with achieving the long-term benefits; individuals with the collective and the social community» [1, p. 13]. In this view, «promotion the human factor» can be understood as guaranteeing the rights and duties of all citizens; enhancing the quality of their material and spiritual life; catering for their immediate needs and long-term benefits. This is the comprehensive view that lay the foundation for many later progressive guidelines on the matter of promoting the human factor in the next National Congresses. In the Fourth Plenum of the Central Committee (7th), the Party stated that: «Human is the most precious resource, and caring for the people's happiness is the most important objective of our nation... We need to fully understand the great values and the decisive nature of the human factor, and all creations, all wealth and culture, all civilization of nations must come from the humane goal of comprehensive human development, the construction of an equal and kind society and the establishment of strong, progressive bonds between people both during production and in daily life» [2, p. 5].

Regarding the subject of the human factor in the nation's industrialization and modernization, the Eighth National Congress (1996) stated: «Improving the general intellect, nurturing and promoting the great potentials of the Vietnamese people are the decisive factors to the success of our nation's industrialization and modernization» [3, p. 87]. According to this, the human factor is the most important element and the main source of motivation that helps create the labor force – the decisive factor to the rate and the stable development of the new production method in the age of globaliza-

tion. Therefore, in order to maintain stability in the process of industrialization and modernization, it is vital to care for the human development, as human is both the aim and the driving force of the social development.

After the Eighth National Congress, the Party has issued many guidelines, decisions as well as solutions to nurture and promote the human factor. In the Report on some theoretical-practical issues after 20 years of reform (1986-2006), the Party stated: «Human is the most precious resource and the development of human is both the motivation and the aim of the revolution and the cause of national reform; it is important to attach the human factor to compassion so the people can develop comprehensively, live in an equal and kind society with healthy human relationship» [4, p. 78-79]. In the Eleventh National Congress, more specifically in the *Platform for building the nation in the transition period to socialism* (complemented, developed in 2011), the Party stated: «The people are the center of the development strategy, and at the same time the subject of development» [5, p. 76]. In order to fulfill the objective has been identified, the Party clearly pointed out the need to «enhance democracy, promote the human factor to its utmost potential; regard human as the subject, the major resource and the aim of development» [5, p. 100]. In fact, this is the continuation of the Party's view that human is the subject and the most important resource, determining the outcome of social development and of the Vietnam revolution. All economic-social developments have to serve the benefits of the people.

In the Twelfth National Congress (2016), the Party stated that «Developing the Vietnamese people comprehensively to meet the requirements for stable national development and the defense of our socialist nation» [6, p. 78] has to be an objective of the development strategy. This is a progress in the awareness of the Party after 30 years of reform, which is suitable to the new demands; this indicates that the Party is putting more emphasis on the indispensable role of

forming and developing comprehensive people, meeting the requirements of building and developing the nation in this age of deep globalization and deep integration. Besides, the Party stated that, apart from promoting the human factor, it is also important to eliminate the negative aspects of people: «Fight against the evil, lowly and outdated behaviors; against the wrong-doings and erroneous opinions that negatively affect the construction of culture and corrupt the people. There need to be measures taken to push back demoralization and improve the limitations of the Vietnamese people» [6, p. 127]. Therefore, it is necessary to: «Promote the human factor in every aspect of social life; focus on building the people's morality, personality, lifestyle, intellect and working abilities; form a healthy cultural environment» [6, p. 219].

Promote the human factor in building the modern Vietnam People's Army.

Under the absolute and direct leadership in all aspects of the Communist Party of Vietnam, for 75 years of building, fighting and maturing, the Vietnam People's Army always acknowledge the importance of improving overall quality, combat strength and fulfilling the political tasks assigned by the Party, State and the people. One of the factors leading to the success of this is the role of the Party committees and Army commanders in popularizing the Party's view of the position and the role of human and promoting the human factor in the revolutionary process; having clear awareness of the decisive role of the human factor to military operations, therefore, proposing suitable guidelines and policies to promote the human factor in building an army capable of fulfilling all assigned tasks.

Under the light of the Party's reform path in promoting the human factor in the revolutionary cause, together with the direct leadership of the Central Military Commission, Party committees on all levels in the army, the human factor in the army is being evaluated more objectively and utilized effectively. With the belief that human is the most important factor, playing a decisive

role in the successful implementation of key political missions, different units in the army have proposed many policies and solutions to enhance the role of officers and soldiers in accomplishing missions. Therefore, the general quality and capacity of officers and soldiers are being improved quickly. «Generations of officers and soldiers have consistently expressed their perseverant belief in the ideal fight for national liberation and socialism; strongly believed in the guidelines and the military art of the Party, in the weapons, equipment and combat strength of our army; always emphasized the importance of responsibility, willing to master their weapons and equipment; actively engaged in training, ready for combat, labor and work; ready to accept and fulfill all tasks assigned» [8, p. 3], directly enhanced the overall quality, readiness for combat and combat strength of our army.

At the present, the cause of reforming, constructing and protecting the country is placing human at the center position, being both the aim and the motivation of the economic-social development. Complicated global and regional situations; trade and technology wars, conflicts over sovereignty; armed conflicts, terrorist, cyber attacks and unconventional security issues are on the rise. The objective of building a «revolutionary, regular, elite, gradually modernized» army with the influence of the Fourth Industrial Revolution leading to renewal of weapons, equipment military science and art result in the over-emphasis on the role of weapons while underestimating the importance of the human factor in building the modern army.

This situation is requiring the Party committees and military commanders in the army to continue popularizing the Party's view on promoting the human factor in military operations, directly enhance the modernization process, the overall quality, combat strength, contributing to an «elite, compact, fast» army, guaranteeing success in every assigned task.

The overall quality and combat strength of the army consist of many factors, among

which human and weapons are the two most basic, and the human factor plays the decisive role. The human factor in building the army is the combination of the physical and intellectual strength, personality and capability of each individual as well as the collective, which is materialized through their actions aiming at fulfilling the revolutionary ideal; the tasks and responsibilities of a soldier, which decide the outcome of the missions. Therefore, the promotion of the human factor in building the military is the combination of different methods and solutions to enhance and spread positivity, creativity, potentials and strong points of each officer and soldier as well as the collective of officers and soldiers as the subject of military operations; at the same time, is the limitation and correction of obstacles that obstruct the army's positivity, therefore, contributes to the overall quality and combat strength, aiding the army in successfully fulfilling assigned tasks.

In order to promote the human factor in building the modern army, it is necessary to take synchronous measures, with heavy focus on the following:

First, continue to raise the awareness of the Party's committees and military commanders in the entire army on the role of every officer and soldier in building the modern army.

This is a matter of much importance in promoting the role of officers and soldiers in building the army; directly determining the overall quality, combat strength of our modern army. It is because practical human activities are activities of purposes, organized and placed under the control of their awareness. The awareness of the Party's committees and military commanders directly affects to the entire process of promoting the role of officers and soldiers in building the army, from creating the leaders' guidelines and policies to making plans to materialize them; to choose the proper contents, forms and measures to promote the potentials and strengths of officers and soldiers in a suitable and scientific way. Awareness is also the basis for unanimity of ideas and actions of

the Party's committees and military commanders to enhance the overall quality of this process.

In this process, first and foremost, it is necessary to raise the awareness of the Party's committees and military leaders on the basics of Marxism-Leninism, Ho Chi Minh's ideology, the Party's view on the matter of human and promoting the human factor; especially, on the decisive role of the human factor to weapons, technical equipment in the cause of building the army and defending the country at the present; on the guidelines and policies from the superior authorities on the process of recruitment, training, usage as well as the planning of policies of officers, soldiers and their families, etc. Besides, it is also importance to raise the Party's committees and military commanders in the entire army on the purpose, the meaning, the content and the method of promoting the role of officers and soldiers in fulfilling assigned missions and building the army. Each level of the Party's committees and military commanders or each body and unit in the entire military to focus on the role of activeness, creativity, responsibility and raise the potentials, intellect and physical strength of each officer, soldier and the collective, creating the great driving force to improve the overall quality, combat strength of each body and unit in the army.

Second, it is necessary to pay attention to forming and nurturing the overall traits and capacity for officers and soldiers to meet the requirements of the assigned tasks.

The Party's consistent guideline in the national reform is to «develop comprehensive people», «promote the human factor in every aspect of social life», focusing on morality, personality, lifestyle, intellect and working ability... Therefore, promoting the role of officers and soldiers in building the army necessitates the construction and nurture a fully developed personality in political quality, morality, lifestyle; in the power of awareness and practical military operations, so that officers and soldiers in the army can

meet the requirements and be able to adapt to every situation in achieving tasks.

It is necessary to carry out the education and training successfully on officers and soldiers in the army. Also, it is important to increase on the politics, ideology, morality and lifestyle training; to combine traditional education with legal training to form and strengthen the army's political and moral quality. Officers and soldiers must have a strong political awareness, pure revolutionary morality, belief, the will to fight and win, the revolutionary caution and self-discipline [8, p. 5]. And this education process must be self-made. Moreover, it is essential to maintain the discipline in each body and unit. Also, officers and soldiers need to be trained in discipline, formal behaviors, perseverance; proper attitudes and behaviors; especially, absolute obedience towards superior orders; willingness to overcome difficulties, readiness to accept and fulfill every assigned task.

Furthermore, it is important to reform and improve the training quality so as to form soldiers and officers' combat quality, meeting the demands of modern warfare. Also, it is necessary to actively renew the contents, forms and methods of training and battle exercise; to put great emphasis on synchronized and professional training that is close to reality and the missions, the options, the objects, the battlefield... and the cyberspace; suitable to the personnel organization and the development of weapons, equipment and military art in Vietnam. Also, the technical, tactical, physical and weapon, especially modern weapons, training must be developed; the training of mobility, cooperation between different branches of the armed forces; the training of defending against natural disasters and rescuing civilians; combining military training with political education, discipline training, strengthening the belief in the assigned weapons and the tactics and military art of Vietnam [8, p. 6]. By these means, the quality and combat ability, especially the elements of politics-spirituality and discipline, of our soldiers will be improved.

Third, it is important to guarantee the material and spiritual life of soldiers; form a healthy and diverse cultural environment in military units.

Caring for the material and spiritual life of soldiers is basically materializing the policies of the Party and State regarding the soldiers themselves, with an aim to directly motivating the promotion of the human factor in military activities. Whether the self-discipline and creativity of officers and soldiers are well-utilized or not depends much on the care and assurance towards their rightful material and spiritual life. This is, first and foremost, the duty of the Party's committees and military commanders, which needs to be carefully led and operated. Apart from the political element, it is important to care for the material and spiritual life of both the soldiers and their families. On the other hand, it is important to promote self-reliance, to organize labor work to improve both the material and spiritual life of the soldiers.

Besides, it is necessary to form a healthy, diverse and truly democratic cultural environment in every body and unit of the army. The Party that «constructing a healthy cultural environment» enable human to promote their talents and intellect. The military cultural environment plays a direct role in nurturing and developing the personality of soldiers, raising the levels of intellect, awareness, consistent political belief, class consciousness; morality, sentiment, spirit, aesthetic values and practical capability of soldiers; directly contributing to the successful implementation of the unit's political objectives. Therefore, there must be strong bonds within the military collective, for instance, between officers and soldiers, between comrades and teammates, between superiors and subordinates, between individuals and collectives, and between the military and the people. That must be an environment with the atmosphere of democracy of close relationship and, yet, high discipline. The unit must be a home where each officer and soldier are willing to take responsibility for the community, contribute

their physical and intellectual capacity to strengthen the unit.

Fourth, promoting the self-reliance and creativity of officers and soldiers in fulfilling tasks.

The origin of the development of each and every object and phenomenon comes from themselves. The self-reliance and creativity of officers and soldiers is the most direct and decisive factor to the formation and development of their quality and capability. The purpose of promoting the human factor in the army is to strengthen the creativity of officers and soldiers in military activities. Therefore, first and foremost, the Party's committees and military commanders have to properly provide education and training for the officers and soldiers, leading to their right attitude and motivation; never be satisfied with their achievements and always strive for higher targets. Each officer and soldier have to plan their own training regime, in which the content and requirements have to be clearly acknowledged on the basis of self-evaluation and reflection on the requirements of the assigned tasks. Each level has to well organize competitive campaigns, adapt the goals of the campaigns in a suitable manner to the reality of the unit; raise the quality of assessment; timely honor and reward individuals and collectives with

noticeable achievements to serve as examples of outstanding individuals. This will motivate both materially and spiritually the officers and soldiers to study and train. The Party's committees and military commanders on all levels in different bodies and units must care for, as well as strictly manage, and facilitate officers and soldiers to self-study, self-research, self-train; regard this as a criterion to categorize the quality of partisans, union members and evaluate the annual task achievement of individuals and units.

Conclusion.

The awareness of the Communist Party of Vietnam on the position and the role of human and promoting the human factor in constructing and defending our nation, after each National Congress, succeed and amend the previous according to the practical requirements of new times. Those views have formed the basic scientific theory to promote the human factor in building the modern army. Well promoting the human factor in military activities will contribute greatly to and determine directly the overall quality and combat strength of our army, making the Vietnam People's Army «elite, compact and fast», meeting the requirements of new missions, guaranteeing the success in achieving every assigned task.

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